

Evaluation of Cognitive Load While Performing Code Comprehension Tasks – Exit Survey

What is your age range?

- 18-20
 - 21-23
 - 24-26
 - 27-29
 - 30+
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What is your gender?

- Man
 - Woman
 - Non-binary / third gender
 - Prefer not to say
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What is your current cumulative GPA?

- 3.8 – 4.0
 - 3.5 – 3.79
 - 3.0 – 3.49
 - 2.5 – 2.99
 - Below 2.5
 - Prefer not to say
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How many years have you worked with Java?

- None
 - Less than a year
 - 1-2 years
 - 3-4 years
 - 5 or more years
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How frequently do you use LLM-based tools (e.g., ChatGPT, Copilot) for programming tasks?

- Never
 - Rarely
 - Occasionally
 - Frequently
 - Very frequently
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Have you previously used an LLM to assist with code comprehension or reviews?

Yes

No

Overall, which code comprehension condition did you prefer?

Code comprehension with LLM assistance

Code comprehension without LLM assistance

No preference

To what extent did you trust the output provided by the LLM during the code comprehension tasks? Please explain your reasoning.

Did the LLM ever change how you approached reading the code? If so, how?
